

Phytochemical and Antioxidant Characterization of Myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) Fruit

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Abstract

Myrtus communis L. is a plant grown in the Mediterranean region, with fruits containing phytochemical compounds important for health. In this study, the phenolic and flavonoid contents, antioxidant capacity, and major organic acid profiles of black myrtle fruits sourced from Muğla and harvested during the 2023-2024 period were investigated. The analyses showed that myrtle fruit possesses high phenolic (319.66 mg GAE L⁻¹) and flavonoid (372.00 mg QE mL⁻¹) contents along with strong antioxidant activity (77.00%). HPLC results revealed gentisic (33.25 mg 100g⁻¹) and ellagic acids (8.79 mg 100g⁻¹) as the dominant phenolic compounds, and tartaric acid (265.33 mg 100g⁻¹) as the main organic acid. Correlation and principal component analyses indicated that phenolic compounds enhance antioxidant capacity, whereas organic acids have a negative effect on phenolic content. The principal component analysis explained 100% of the variance in the biochemical composition. This study provides systematic data on the chemical and biological potential of myrtle fruits grown in Türkiye, contributing original information to the literature.

Research Article

Article History

Received :12.09.2025

Accepted :25.10.2025

Keywords

Muğla
Myrtus communis L.
berry fruit
myrtle

1. Introduction

M. communis L., belonging to the family *Myrtaceae*, is a perennial aromatic plant species native to Europe, North Africa, Western Asia and India. In Türkiye, it grows naturally along the Mediterranean coastal regions, particularly in the provinces of Adana, Antalya, Mersin and Muğla (Oğur, 1994). As one of the characteristic species of the Mediterranean Basin, this plant has been traditionally used for both nutritional and medicinal purposes for centuries. Its fruits ripen between October and February, displaying color variations ranging from white-yellow to blue-black. The black-fruited types are predominantly found around the Antalya region, while the white-fruited ones are common in the maquis ecosystems of Muğla and its surroundings. In recent years, the growing awareness of healthy eating has increased the demand for natural products free from artificial additives (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2013). This trend has particularly emphasized the importance of fruit-derived products rich in polyphenols, flavonoids and organic acids. Numerous studies have demonstrated that the fruits and leaves of *M. communis* possess antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and hepatoprotective properties (Gülçin et al., 2019; Dabbou et al., 2020; Yousefi et al., 2020; Bouyahya et al., 2021; Ben Hsouna et al., 2022; Dindar et al., 2023). In addition, traditionally consumed myrtle-based products have been reported to support digestive health, reduce free radical damage and lower cardiovascular risks (Ben Cheikh et al., 2021; Oueslati et al., 2022). Natural products rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids and anthocyanins exhibit high antioxidant and antimicrobial activities and are therefore consumed as health-promoting foods (Johnston and Gaas, 2006; Budak et al., 2014; Gullón et al., 2020; Pepe et al., 2023). Myrtle fruit, due to its phytochemical richness, represents a notable local resource for supporting immune function and metabolic health (Yılmaz and Tokuşoğlu, 2021; Dursun et al., 2022). However, systematic scientific data regarding its phenolic compound profile, organic acid content and antioxidant capacity

remain very limited. Phenolic compounds, especially polyphenols, flavonoids, and anthocyanins, are active biological molecules widely found in plants and can effectively neutralize free radicals. This compound exhibits antioxidant activity through mechanisms such as hydrogen atom transfer, single-electron transfer, sequential proton-electron transfer, and chelation of transition metals (Zeb, 2020). This has made it possible to prevent the reduction of damage caused by oxidative stress and contribute to the reduction of many chronic diseases such as cancer and inflammatory diseases (Pandey and Rizvi, 2009). The fruit of *M. communis* L. is particularly rich in gallic acid, ellagic acid, catechin, quercetin, and anthocyanin, and exhibits a high total phenolic content and potent DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP antioxidants through various processes (Gardeli et al., 2008; Tuberoso et al., 2010; Yeğın et al., 2022). It has been reported that genotype, vegetation, and maturity stage significantly influence the phenolic profile and antioxidant capacity of myrtle fruit (Hennia et al., 2018). Therefore, detailed examination of the phenolic compound composition and antioxidant activity of *M. communis* L. fruit is of great importance both in terms of understanding the bioactive potential and providing a scientific basis for studies on the cultivation of plants beneficial to health. This study aimed to determine the phenolic compound profile, organic acid content and antioxidant capacity of fruit juice obtained from naturally growing black myrtle fruits in the Muğla province. By systematically characterizing the chemical constituents of myrtle fruits grown in Türkiye, this study provides a unique dataset to the scientific literature.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material

In this study, naturally growing *M. communis* L. (black myrtle) fruits were collected in September and October of 2023-2024 from the Muğla province. The harvested fruits were cleaned and sorted, then pressed to obtain fruit juice. The freshly obtained juices

were prepared under sterile conditions and stored at +4 °C for subsequent biochemical analyses. The analyses included determination of chemical composition, phenolic and flavonoid contents, antioxidant capacity and organic acid profiles, with all measurements performed in triplicate.

2.2. Sample extraction

For the determination of phenolic compounds and antioxidant activities, 10 g of fruit juice sample was mixed with 50 mL of methanol and continuously stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. Following extraction, the mixture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 minutes and the supernatant was filtered using filter paper. The resulting extract was stored at +4 °C until further analyses were performed.

2.3. Determination of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the fruit juice samples was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method (Gamez-Meza et al., 1999). Prior to analysis, all samples were passed through a membrane filter to remove particulate matter. Gallic acid was used as the standard phenolic compound for calibration. Methanolic standard solutions at various concentrations were prepared and their absorbance values were measured spectrophotometrically at 765 nm. The obtained data were used to calculate the total phenolic content, expressed as mg GAE L⁻¹.

2.4. Determination of total flavonoid content

The total flavonoid content of the fruit juice samples was determined using a colorimetric method based on the formation of an aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) complex (Woisky and Salatino, 1998). Prior to analysis, the samples were diluted with distilled water to appropriate concentrations within the measurement range. Quercetin (QE) was used as the standard compound for calibration and methanolic solutions at different concentrations were prepared, with absorbance measurements performed at 415 nm. The results were used to calculate the total flavonoid content, expressed as µg QE mL⁻¹. This method allows for the sensitive and reliable quantitative analysis of

flavonoid compounds in the samples.

2.5. Analysis of phenolic compounds by HPLC

Phenolic compounds in the fruit juice samples were analyzed using an Agilent 1260 HPLC system. Chromatographic separation was performed on an ACE-C18 column (4.6 mm x 150 mm, 5 µm particle size), with a mobile phase consisting of water containing 0.02% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (Phase A) and methanol containing 0.02% TFA (Phase B). The flow rate was set at 0.5 mL min⁻¹ and the column temperature was maintained constant throughout the analysis. The gradient elution program was as follows: starting at 25% B, increased to 30% B between 5-10 min, to 45% B between 10-16 min, held at 45% B from 16-18 min, increased to 80% B from 18-25 min, held at 80% B from 25-30 min and finally returned to 25% B from 30-40 min (Wen et al., 2005). This method allows for detailed and reproducible analysis of phenolic compounds present in the fruit juice samples.

2.6. Quantification of organic acids and phenolic compounds by HPLC-UV

Organic acids and phenolic compounds in the fruit juice samples were quantitatively analyzed using an Agilent 1260 HPLC system. Chromatographic separation was performed on an ACE-C18 column (4 mm x 150 mm, 5 µm; Hichrom Ltd.). The analysis was carried out using an isocratic elution method with a 10 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 2.2) as the mobile phase. The flow rate was set at 1 mL min⁻¹ and the injection volume was 20 µL. Detection was performed at 245 nm for ascorbic acid and at 210 nm for other organic acids (Fu et al., 2005). This procedure allows for sensitive and reproducible quantitative determination of organic acids and phenolic compounds in the fruit juice samples.

2.7. Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity of the fruit juice samples was determined using the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) method with minor modifications (Ebrahimzadeh et al., 2008). The DPPH stock solution (6 x 10⁻⁵ M) was prepared by dissolving 0.0024 g of DPPH in

100 mL of methanol. The working solution was diluted with methanol to a final concentration of 40 mg L⁻¹. For the analysis, 300 µL of fruit juice sample was mixed with 5700 µL of DPPH solution in 10 mL tubes, vortexed and then incubated at room temperature in the dark for 60 minutes. After incubation, absorbance values were measured at 517 nm using a Shimadzu UV-1800 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The control solution was prepared without the sample and measured at the same wavelength. The percentage of antioxidant activity (AA) was calculated based on the obtained absorbance values using the following formula:

$$\text{Antioxidant activity (\%)} = \left[\frac{AC(O)_{517} - AA(t)_{517}}{AC(O)_{517}} \right] \times 100$$

Here, AC(O)₅₁₇, represents the absorbance of the control at t = 0 min. and AA(t)₅₁₇ represents the absorbance of the sample after t = 1 hour.

2.8. Statistical analyses

All data analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics (v.21.0). Measurements were conducted in triplicate for each compound and the statistical reliability of the results was assessed based on these replicates. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were employed to examine the obtained data. For each biochemical parameter, the mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation were calculated to generate descriptive statistics, while the direction and strength of linear relationships between parameters were determined using Pearson correlation coefficients. PCA was applied to better reveal multivariate relationships and to explain the variance in the data through principal components and the results were presented in tabular form.

3. Findings and Discussion

The phytochemical analysis results of *M. communis* L. fruit are shown in Table 1. The mean total phenolic content was determined as 319.66 mg GAE L⁻¹, and the total flavonoid content was 372.00 mg QE mL⁻¹. These high levels of phenolics and flavonoids suggested that the fruit is a strong source of antioxidants.

The mean antioxidant activity measured by DPPH was 77%, indicating that phenolic compounds contributed significantly to this activity. Among the phenolic compounds, gentisic acid was the most abundant, followed by ellagic acid; caffeic, protocatechuic, and coumaric acids were also detected. The coefficients of variation ranged from 2.27% to 10.06%, showing a generally consistent distribution of phenolic compounds among the samples. In the organic acid analysis, tartaric acid was the predominant compound, followed by acetic and oxalic acids, whereas citric acid was found at the lowest concentration. The distribution of these organic acids was found to support the characteristic taste and aromatic properties of the fruit and to contribute to its microbiological stability. These findings indicated that *M. communis* L. fruit is not only rich in phenolic compounds and flavonoids but also possesses a high antioxidant capacity, enhancing its functional properties. Moreover, these results were considered to be potentially influenced by regional climatic conditions, soil characteristics, and environmental stress factors, suggesting that the phenolic and organic acid contents may vary according to the fruit's adaptation and response to environmental conditions. This highlights that the nutritional value and health-promoting properties of myrtle fruits may differ depending on ecosystem conditions. In this study, the amounts of different phenolic and organic acid components, as well as antioxidant capacities were determined and compared with similar findings reported in the literature. Bakar (2020) reported that the total phenolic content of fresh Hambeles fruits grown in the Osmaniye and Mersin regions ranged from 26.88 to 43.01 mg GAE L⁻¹, while total flavonoid content ranged from 15.65 to 23.42 mg QE mL⁻¹. These values are in agreement with the high antioxidant capacity observed in our study. Similarly, Kayımu (2017) reported that the total phenol and flavonoid contents of *M. communis* L. fruit extracts ranged from 5.1 to 45.2 mg 100 g⁻¹ and 2.3 to 11.6 mg 100 g⁻¹, respectively, with the aqueous extract showing the highest antioxidant capacity. In our study, the mean

antioxidant activity measured by DPPH was 77%, supporting the high antioxidant capacities reported in the literature. Among the phenolic compounds, gentisic acid was found at the highest concentration, followed by ellagic acid; caffeic, protocatechic and coumaric acids were also identified. The coefficients of variation ranged from 2.27% to 10.06%, indicating a generally consistent distribution of phenolic compounds among the samples. These findings suggest that the phenolic profile and antioxidant capacity of myrtle fruits are influenced by both genotype and environmental factors. In organic acid analyses, tartaric acid was identified as the predominant compound, followed by acetic and oxalic acids, while citric acid was present at the lowest concentration. The distribution of these organic acids likely contributes to the characteristic taste and aromatic properties of the fruit, as well as its microbiological stability. Çetin (2022) reported that the essential oil content of leaves from different myrtle genotypes varied depending on seasonal and ontogenetic factors, with gentisic and ellagic acids being predominant; this is

consistent with our finding of gentisic acid as the major phenolic compound. Additionally, Çınar (2018) demonstrated that polyphenol oxidase enzyme could be suppressed by 40-100% by various inhibitors, potentially affecting the antioxidant capacity of phenolic compounds. Yılmaz (2020) reported that the antioxidant capacities, total phenol contents, and bioavailability of *M. communis* L. fruits varied at different ripening stages, which aligns with our findings on phenolic content and antioxidant activity. Overall, these results indicate that the phenolic and organic acid components of *M. communis* L. fruit contribute significantly to its high antioxidant potential. Furthermore, the observed variations in fruit composition may be influenced by regional production conditions, climate, soil characteristics, and environmental stress factors, suggesting that the phenolic and organic acid content can be shaped by the fruit's adaptive responses. These findings highlight that the nutritional value and health benefits of myrtle fruits may vary depending on the ecological conditions in which they are grown.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of biochemical parameters of *M. communis* L. fruit

Variable	Abbreviation	Unit	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ± Std. Dev.	%CV
Total Phenolic	TPC	mg GAE L ⁻¹	318.0	322.0	319.66±2.08	0.65
Total Flavonoids	TFC	mg QE mL ⁻¹	370.0	374.0	372.00±2.00	0.53
Antioxidant activity (DPPH)	AntAc	%	75.0	79.0	77.00±2.00	2.59
Phenolic Compounds						
Protocatechic Acid	ProA	mg 100g ⁻¹	2.84	3.07	2.97±0.11	3.70
Gentisic Acid	GenA	mg 100g ⁻¹	31.71	34.36	33.25±1.37	4.12
Caffeic Acid	CafA	mg 100g ⁻¹	2.66	3.25	2.98±0.30	10.06
Coumaric Acid	CoumA	mg 100g ⁻¹	1.45	1.75	1.58±0.15	9.49
Ellagic Acid	EllA	mg 100g ⁻¹	8.59	9.00	8.79±0.20	2.27
Organic Acids						
Oxalic Acid	OxA	mg 100g ⁻¹	122	130	127.00±4.35	3.42
Tartaric Acid	TarA	mg 100g ⁻¹	262	269	265.33±3.51	1.32
Acetic Acid	AceA	mg 100g ⁻¹	208	226	218.33±9.29	4.25
Citric Acid	CitA	mg 100g ⁻¹	1.9	2.0	1.96±0.05	2.55

Table 2 shows the relationships between phenolic compounds, organic acids, and antioxidant activity parameters in *M. communis* L. fruit juice samples using Pearson correlation coefficients (PCA). The results indicated both strong positive and negative correlations among the parameters. A very strong positive correlation was observed

between total phenolic content, total flavonoid content and DPPH values. These findings suggest that the total phenolic and flavonoid contents directly contribute to the antioxidant capacity of the fruit juice. The parallel increase of antioxidant activity with the amount of phenolic compounds supports the notion that the biological activity of the juice largely

originates from these compounds. Significant positive correlations were found among the phenolic compounds protocatechuic acid, gentisic acid and caffeic acid, indicating that these hydroxybenzoic and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives may be formed via similar biosynthetic pathways and tend to increase together. However, coumaric acid showed a significant negative correlation with these compounds, suggesting that its synthesis or conversion processes may be biochemically opposed to those of the other phenolic acids. Among the organic acids, a strong positive correlation was observed between oxalic acid and citric acid. Additionally, tartaric acid exhibited strong positive correlations with caffeic acid and gentisic acid. These findings indicate that the organic acid profile and phenolic acid composition of the fruit juice tend to vary together to some extent. Negative

correlations revealed that citric acid had strong inverse relationships with total phenolic content, total flavonoid content and DPPH values, indicating that samples with higher citric acid levels exhibited lower total phenolic content and antioxidant activity. Similarly, oxalic acid also displayed negative correlations with these parameters, suggesting a tendency for reduced phenolic accumulation in samples with higher organic acid levels. Overall, the correlation analysis demonstrated that phenolic compounds are strongly positively interrelated, whereas citric and oxalic acids exhibit inverse relationships with these compounds. These results highlight that the chemical composition of myrtle fruit juice is closely associated with its antioxidant capacity, with total phenolic content being one of the key factors determining its biological activity.

Table 2. Pearson correlation analysis of *M. communis* L.

		TPC	TFC	DPPH	ProA	GenA	CafA	CoumA	Ella	OxaA	TarA	AceA	CitA
TPC	r	1	0.96	0.96	-0.02	0.03	-0.05	0.05	0.73	-0.93	-0.31	0.52	-0.97
	p		0.17	0.17	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.47	0.22	0.79	0.64	0.15
TFC	r	0.96	1	1.00**	-0.29	-0.23	-0.33	0.32	0.51	-0.80	-0.56	0.26	-0.86
	p	0.17		0.00	0.80	0.84	0.78	0.78	0.65	0.40	0.61	0.82	0.33
DPPH	r	0.96	1.00**	1	-0.29	-0.23	-0.33	0.32	0.51	-0.80	-0.56	0.26	-0.86
	p	0.17	0.00		0.80	0.84	0.78	0.78	0.65	0.40	0.61	0.82	0.33
ProA	r	-0.02	-0.29	-0.29	1	0.99*	0.99*	-0.99*	0.66	-0.33	0.95	0.84	-0.22
	p	0.98	0.80	0.80		0.03	0.02	0.02	0.53	0.78	0.19	0.36	0.85
GenA	r	0.03	-0.23	-0.23	0.99*	1	0.99	-0.99	0.71	-0.38	0.93	0.87	-0.27
	p	0.97	0.84	0.84	0.03		0.06	0.05	0.49	0.74	0.23	0.32	0.82
CafA	r	-0.05	-0.33	-0.33	0.99*	0.99	1	-1.00**	0.63	-0.29	0.96	0.81	-0.18
	p	0.96	0.78	0.78	0.02	0.06		0.00	0.55	0.81	0.16	0.39	0.88
CoumA	r	0.05	0.32	0.32	-0.99*	-0.99	-1.00**	1	-0.64	0.30	-0.96	0.82	0.18
	p	0.96	0.78	0.78	0.02	0.05	0.00		0.55	0.80	0.17	0.38	0.87
Ella	r	0.73	0.51	0.51	0.66	0.71	0.63	-0.64	1	-0.92	0.41	0.96	-0.87
	p	0.47	0.65	0.65	0.53	0.49	0.55	0.55		0.25	0.72	0.16	0.32
OxaA	r	-0.93	-0.80	-0.80	-0.33	-0.38	-0.29	0.30	-0.92	1	-0.03	-0.79	0.99
	p	0.22	0.40	0.40	0.78	0.74	0.81	0.80	0.25		0.97	0.42	0.07
TarA	r	-0.31	-0.56	-0.56	0.95	0.93	0.96	-0.96	0.41	-0.03	1	0.63	0.08
	p	0.79	0.61	0.61	0.19	0.23	0.16	0.17	0.72	0.97		0.55	0.94
AceA	r	0.52	0.26	0.26	0.84	0.87	0.81	-0.82	0.96	-0.79	0.63	1	-0.71
	p	0.64	0.82	0.82	0.36	0.32	0.39	0.38	0.16	0.42	0.55		0.49
CitA	r	-0.97	-0.86	-0.86	-0.22	-0.27	-0.18	0.18	-0.87	0.99	0.08	-0.71	1
	p	0.15	0.33	0.33	0.85	0.82	0.88	0.87	0.32	0.07	0.94	0.49	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. Pearson Correlation: r; significance: p

These analysis results indicate significant relationships among phenolic compounds, organic acids and antioxidant activity parameters in *M. communis* L. fruit juice samples. The strong positive correlations observed between total phenolic content, total flavonoid content and DPPH values

demonstrate that phenolic compounds directly contribute to the antioxidant capacity of the fruit juice. This finding is consistent with the results of Güzel and Elmastaş (2019), who reported that the highest antioxidant activity in *M. communis* L. seed and peel extracts paralleled high phenolic compound levels.

Similarly, Bakar (2020) reported that phenolic compounds in myrtle fruits tend to decrease during maturation, whereas organic acid levels (malic and citric acids) increase; this trend is supported in the present study by the observed negative correlations between organic acids and phenolic content. Moreover, the negative correlation of coumaric acid with other phenolic acids suggests, as emphasized by Bakar (2020), that this compound may follow a different biosynthetic pathway during fruit maturation. The strong positive correlations observed among organic acids align with the findings of Toker (2016), who reported that organic acid components in myrtle fruit change in parallel during heating and concentration processes. Additionally, Yaşa et al. (2023) noted that the phytochemical content of *M. communis* L. fruits from different regions varies depending on environmental and climatic conditions, supporting the notion that the negative correlations between organic acids and phenolic compounds in this study may arise from ecological factors. Bakar (2020) also indicated that the decrease in phenolic acids is associated with maturation and potentially with increased acidity levels. The positive relationship observed between ellagic acid and acetic acid in the present study is consistent with Toker (2016), who reported rearrangement and concentration increases in phenolic compounds during thermal processing. Furthermore, the high linoleic acid levels reported by Güzel and Elmastaş (2019) in *M. communis* L. extracts, which contribute to antioxidant capacity, support the phenolic acid interactions observed in this study in terms of the oxidative stability of the juice. Overall, the correlation analysis demonstrates that the phenolic and organic acid composition of *M. communis* L. fruit juice is complex but significantly interrelated. Total phenolic and flavonoid contents were identified as key determinants of antioxidant activity, whereas samples with high citric and oxalic acid levels exhibited reduced phenolic accumulation. These results indicate that the chemical composition of *M. communis* L. fruit varies with both maturation and regional conditions and that these variations directly affect its

biological activity. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results presented in Table 3 revealed the relationships among the biochemical components of myrtle fruit and indicated that the total variation in the data was explained by two principal components. This suggests that the selected parameters were sufficient to represent the chemical composition of the fruit. The first component exhibited high positive loadings for phenolic compounds, particularly gentisic and ellagic acids, as well as for the organic acid acetic acid, suggesting that these compounds may be synthesized through similar biochemical pathways. The grouping of these compounds along the same PCA axis implies that they likely share a common biochemical or metabolic route. The high loading of acetic acid indicates that it is a dominant component and positively associated with phenolic compounds. In contrast, the negative loading of coumaric acid suggests that this compound may follow a metabolic trend opposite to that of other phenolic acids. Similarly, the negative loadings of oxalic and citric acids indicate that in samples with higher organic acid content, the accumulation of phenolic compounds may be reduced. These findings support a potential inverse relationship between the organic acid profile and the synthesis of phenolic metabolites. The second principal component showed high positive correlations with total phenolic content, total flavonoid content and antioxidant activity, highlighting the determining role of phenolic compounds in the antioxidant capacity of the fruit. This indicates that the antioxidant potential of myrtle fruit largely derives from its phenolic composition. Overall, the PCA findings suggest that phenolic compounds in myrtle fruit are positively associated with antioxidant activity but negatively associated with organic acids, indicating two complementary metabolic orientations within the fruit's chemical structure. The increase in phenolic compounds is generally considered a reflection of the plants defense mechanism against oxidative stress. In contrast, higher organic acid levels are associated with fruit ripening and metabolic energy cycles. Therefore, the

increase in organic acid levels may lead to reduced accumulation of phenolic compounds, with phenolic structures potentially being degraded through oxidative enzymatic reactions or diverted into metabolic transformation pathways during maturation.

These findings indicate that the biochemical composition of myrtle fruit is governed by a complex metabolic system based on the balance between phenolic and organic acid compounds.

Table 3. The principal component analysis (PCA) results of the biochemical components of *M. communis* L. fruit

Variable	Component 1	Component 2
Total Phenolic	0.45	0.88
Total Flavonoids	0.19	0.98
Antioxidant activity (DPPH)	0.19	0.98
Protocatechic Acid	0.88	-0.47
Gentisic Acid	0.90	-0.42
Cafeic Acid	0.86	-0.50
Coumaric Acid	-0.86	0.50
Ellagic Acid	0.94	0.33
Oxalic Acid	-0.74	-0.67
Tartaric Acid	0.69	-0.71
Acetic Acid	0.99	0.07
Citric Acid	-0.65	-0.75
Eigenvalue	6.71	5.28
Explained variance (%)	55.93	44.06
Cumulative variance (%)	55.93	100.00

These results are further supported by similar findings reported in the literature. Serce et al. (2010) reported that *M. communis* L. fruit extracts exhibited high DPPH activity and total phenolic content ranging from 44.41 to 74.44 mg GAE L⁻¹. This aligns with the high antioxidant potential observed in our study, where PCA analysis indicated that phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity were closely associated. Al-Najjar et al. (2025) identified high levels of anthocyanins (particularly petunidin-3-O-glucoside and malvidin-3-O-rutinoside) in myrtle fruit peel and reported a strong positive correlation of these compounds with antioxidant activity. This finding corresponds with our observation that phenolic compounds in the PCA model grouped along the same axis as antioxidant activity. Similarly, Vega et al. (2025) reported that myrtle fruit peel contains high amounts of polyphenols and anthocyanins, with malvidin-3-O-glucoside being the dominant phenolic compound. In line with our results, where ellagic and gentisic acids were prominent, this emphasizes that the phenolic composition of myrtle fruit is a key determinant of its antioxidant potential. Rashed (2021) also

highlighted that *M. communis* is rich in volatile compounds such as α -pinene, 1,8-cineole and linalool, which contribute to both antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, supporting our finding of the substantial contribution of phenolic compounds to antioxidant capacity. Moreover, Yarahmadi et al. (2024) reported that phenolic content and antioxidant capacity of *M. communis* populations in Iran varied depending on environmental conditions, with particularly high values in the Khoraman and Hormozgan populations. This observation corroborates our finding that the inverse relationship between organic acids and phenolic compounds may be influenced by ecological and climatic factors. Overall, the PCA results, in agreement with the literature, indicate that the phenolic-rich composition of myrtle fruit enhances antioxidant capacity, whereas organic acid accumulation can suppress the synthesis of phenolic metabolites. These findings demonstrate that the biochemical composition of myrtle fruit is sensitive both to genetic factors and to the climatic conditions of its growing environment.

4. Conclusion

This study comprehensively elucidated the phenolic compound profile, organic acid content, and antioxidant capacity of *M. communis* L. fruit. The findings demonstrated that myrtle fruit is rich in phenolic compounds and flavonoids, which serve as the primary determinants of its antioxidant properties. Organic acids were also found to influence phenolic content and antioxidant capacity. The study provides detailed quantitative data that fill gaps in the literature regarding the phytochemical characteristics of *M. communis* L. fruits grown in different regions of Türkiye. In particular, the high phenolic content and strong antioxidant capacity highlight the fruit's potential as a natural source of antioxidants. For future research, comparative analyses of fruits obtained from different ecological regions, maturity stages, and genotypes, as well as investigations into metabolic transformation and storage stability, will enhance understanding of the potential applications of myrtle fruit. Furthermore, studying the interactions between phenolic compounds and organic acids at the molecular level may provide valuable insights into the biochemical mechanisms underlying fruit quality traits. In conclusion, *M. communis* L. fruit is a valuable species in terms of its phenolic composition, organic acid profile, and antioxidant capacity. The results indicate that the fruit can serve as an important natural component for food, health, and industrial applications, providing a solid foundation for further advanced studies in this field.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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To Cite

Alan, F., Çolak, A.M., 2025. Phytochemical and Antioxidant Characterization of Myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) Fruit. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(4): 1182-1193.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17928995>.
